

Plan of action

The Dutch Open Science Monitor

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The Dutch Open Science Monitor by CWTS and Dialogic

CWTS and Dialogic will jointly develop the Dutch Open Science Monitor. The development is taking place through two sub-projects. One aimed at designing a framework for the monitoring and evaluation of Open Science and one aimed at developing a minimum viable product (MVP). In this document, we explain how we do that.

1.1 Subproject 1: Framework for monitoring and evaluation of Open Science

The Netherlands has set up an ambitious programme to embed Open Science in knowledge-creating institutions and their activities. This programme is based on a commitment to values such as quality and integrity, collective benefit, justice and fairness, and diversity and inclusion. The development of a monitoring and evaluation framework that reflects the practices, values and priorities of Dutch stakeholders in the field of knowledge creation is essential to support this programme.

In line with the values of Open Science, all activities described in sub-project 1 will prioritise open, transparent, collaborative and participatory research practices.

1.1.1 What is the current state of affairs?

The first months of the sub-project will consist of a series of landscape studies and reviews. These desktop reviews will provide a comprehensive overview of existing monitoring strategies and policies. A survey will also be prepared to get an overview of the existing practices in the field of Open Science in the Netherlands.

Evaluation of existing monitoring strategies

There are already several initiatives (national and international) aimed at monitoring and evaluating aspects of open research practices. To capitalize on the efforts of these existing initiatives and fine-tune them where possible, we will carefully map them. We focus on four elements: 1) which aspects of Open Science are examined; 2) which data sources and methodologies are used; 3) how data is visualized, and 4) which elements can be reused in this project. Each existing initiative will also be examined to make explicit the scope of Open Science that is used, the assumptions that are made and what strengths and weaknesses are.

Overview of relevant institutional, national and international policies

Knowledge institutions, the national government and international actors all have a policy on Open Science. It is important to have a good overview of this policy in order to

design a good monitor, because the monitor must support future policy-making and implementations. That is why we review existing Open Science policy on the basis of policy documents.

1.1.2 What are the values/needs of stakeholders?

Developing a monitoring strategy for the Netherlands offers a unique opportunity to start a discussion about "the Open Science we want". Although the National Open Science Programme has provided an invaluable basis for this discussion, much more is needed. Therefore, we will consult multiple stakeholder communities to better understand which Open Science practices they apply and/or value, how they assess the value and impact of Open Science, what their vision of Open Science is in the future, and how open research practices relate to recognition and rewards reforms. In addition, it is also important that policymakers can use the monitor for policy evaluations and developments.

Stakeholder mapping

There is a wide range of stakeholders that are important for the development of the monitoring framework. In addition to knowledge-producing communities, our stakeholder mapping will also focus on societal stakeholders who use knowledge. We identify these societal stakeholders through literature research and targeted sampling. CWTS and Dialogic consciously take a broad view of Open Science, including a wide range of scientific contributions (Open Access, FAIR and Open Data, FAIR Open Software) as well as contributions in the field of citizen science and social engagement.

Mapping survey of Open Science practices of scientists

In order to effectively determine how Open Science can be optimally monitored in the Netherlands, we are mapping the ways in which Open Science is currently being practiced. After all, it is important that existing practices can be made visible in the monitor as well as possible. That is why we send a survey to Dutch scientists to ask which Open Science practices they use.

Establishment of a technical/infrastructure advisory board

To ensure that the framework and the resulting dashboard reflect the needs and priorities of the stakeholders, CWTS/Dialogic deliberately chose not to select a specific technical partner(s) at the beginning of the project. Aligning stakeholders' priorities and preferences with technical feasibility will be an important part of the MVP development. To identify and address technical challenges, a technical/infrastructure advisory board will be established at the beginning of the project. It is expected that the council, consisting of a broad representation of various parties, will meet at least once a quarter. Membership of the council is voluntary and unpaid.

Setting up and rolling out community consultation

An important part of this phase is to gain an in-depth understanding of stakeholders' attitudes, values, expectations and vision towards Open Science and its monitoring. These perspectives are collected through (group) interviews and surveys.

Interviews and focus groups

Semi-structured interviews and focus groups will be held with stakeholders to explore their attitudes, values, expectations and vision towards Open Science. Essential for this is being able to ask questions about existing insights, but also inductively collecting insights that are not yet on the radar of our team. These interviews and focus groups also form the basis for the so-called gap analysis, by identifying current challenges and bottlenecks related to a lack of capacity in terms of infrastructure and knowledge, as well as institutional or cultural barriers. Based on the interviews and focus groups, we will identify strategies to make barriers to Open Science negotiable, such as institutional preparedness frameworks, surveys on researchers' perceptions or monitoring of infrastructure.

Validating survey

After completing the qualitative analysis of the interviews, we will send another survey to scientists in the Netherlands. This survey has a more validating character and will test the insights from the qualitative analysis with the scientific community in the Netherlands. This set-up allows us to test the extent to which the phenomena uncovered from the qualitative analysis are recognized and supported in the broader scientific community.

Town halls

Building consensus between the different stakeholders involved in Open Science in the Netherlands is essential for setting up a robust monitoring framework. Such a consensus reflects not only the practices, but also the values of these diverse communities. The consensus building activities will focus around three 'town hall' meetings that will facilitate the discussion among the stakeholders on the results of the focus groups and interviews. Consensus will be fostered through structured and interactive work sessions.

1.1.3 What do we want to achieve in the monitor?

The end point of the sub-project is the development of a framework based on the community consultation, on the basis of which a minimum viable product will be developed in sub-project 2.

Development of the framework

The development of the Open Science Monitoring and Evaluation framework will use the INORMS SCOPE framework for responsible evaluation of research. This framework is based on five core principles outlined below.

Five core principles of the framework

1. Start with what you value: the findings of the surveys, interviews, focus groups and town halls will provide a clear insight into what is valued and of value to Dutch knowledge producers and users.
2. Context considerations: the framework should learn and support strategic decision-making and will therefore collect data at different levels of analysis (individual, institutional, national).
3. Evaluation options: The framework is intended to integrate multiple data sources from both qualitative and quantitative strategies.
4. In-depth reflection: Discussions will take place at all stages of the development of the framework on the potential for biases and unintended consequences of the proposed evaluation strategies.
5. Evaluate the evaluation: The development of the framework will also be accompanied by the development of a systematic approach to consider the extent to which the evaluation achieves its goals and provides both formative and summative insights.

Selection of technology providers

The final step of sub-project 1 is the selection of technical solutions and providers for sub-project 2. This is done in consultation with the technical/infrastructure advisory board and taking into account the monitoring framework.

The selection will look at the technical suitability, legal and organisational aspects (including data management), and the degree of connection to existing infrastructure. In addition to the selection of technical solutions and providers for the development of the dashboard, discussions will also be held with relevant data providers about possibilities to integrate specific data that is currently missing for the Netherlands into future iterations.

1.2 Subproject 2: Development of a minimum viable product (MVP) and future planning

This sub-project focuses on the development of an MVP. Central to the approach taken in this sub-project is the flexibility of the development, reflecting the choice of CWTS and Dialogic for the community-driven bottom-up development of a national Open Science monitoring strategy. The chosen approach means that it is not possible to determine the exact specifications of the dashboard before the community consultations in sub-project 1 have been completed. In addition, we are conducting sub-project 2 in consultation with Open Science NL and other stakeholders. This not only ensures that the priorities of the communities are well reflected in the dashboard

design, but also that the monitor is optimally usable for all relevant stakeholders. The development of the MVP is described below.

1.2.1 Minimum viable product (MVP)

To ensure that the MVP reflects both the findings of sub-project 1 and the preferences of OS-NL, the development of the MVP will take place through co-creation with OS-NL. This will focus in particular on four key aspects that are discussed in detail below.

Selection dashboard interface

We recognize the need from Open Science NL for an open infrastructure where data is offered openly for control and reuse. CWTS/Dialogic has already identified a number of dashboard options that can be tailored for the purposes of this project. While all options offer completely open data, they differ in terms of ownership of the software used for the dashboard. Options range from a dashboard interface built from scratch using free/open-source software, through existing platforms created by CWTS and Dialogic, to commercial platforms that require subscription fees. Each option has advantages and disadvantages that need to be weighed, also in light of the technical capacity it requires to maintain the dashboard after the completion of the tender.

Types of quantitative data used to populate the dashboard

There are numerous strategies for collecting quantitative data related to Open Science. We build on the options outlined in the PathOS Open Science Impact Indicator Handbook, produced by CWTS in collaboration with international partners. It is expected that the quantitative data included in the dashboard will provide an overview of Open Science products, including open science publications (journal articles, preprints, conference proceedings, books, book chapters, etc.), FAIR research data, and Free and Open-Source Software (FOSS). The final selection of indicators and data required for this will take place in consultation with Open Science NL. Where possible, existing data sources will be reused to minimise the administrative burden and future financial costs. In line with the [Barcelona Declaration on Open Research Information](#), which was co-initiated by CWTS and which enjoys broad support in the Netherlands, only open data sources will be used. We will coordinate this as much as possible with developments in the Netherlands in the field of open research information, such as the [Open Research Information Agenda](#) led by SURF and to which CWTS makes an important contribution.

Types of qualitative data used to populate the dashboard

Qualitative data will play an important role in illustrating the impact of Open Science practices, as well as highlighting emerging practices and possible future priorities. We expect qualitative data to include institutional case studies and/or impact narratives. In addition, open questions from the surveys developed in subproject 1 will provide additional sources of qualitative data. To facilitate the creation of this qualitative data, case study templates and ethical guidelines will be developed. In addition, controlled

vocabularies will be developed to annotate case studies and enable the reconciliation of the qualitative data with the quantitative data as described above. A comprehensive data management plan will be developed for the management and long-term storage of the qualitative data generated for the dashboard. To further identify and monitor the impact and change caused by the roll-out of Open Science in the Netherlands, it may also be an option to set up an Open Science panel that meets annually. Members can come from the different stakeholder groups identified in sub-project 1. The topics identified by this panel can also serve as an important source of qualitative data. The final selection of qualitative data sources will take place after coordination with OS-NL, taking into account future capacity and funding constraints.

Data storage and long-term curation

To guarantee the long-term availability of the new data collected for the dashboard, it is necessary to draw up a data management plan in coordination with Open Science NL. In particular, strategic decisions will have to be made about the location of data storage and long-term curation. All data generated for the dashboard will be made available under a CC0 license to facilitate optimal interaction and reuse.

1.2.2 Visualization and reporting

A key priority for data presentation in the dashboard is to avoid siloing between qualitative and quantitative data sources. Instead, we want to present a holistic view of Open Science from multiple perspectives. Achieving such a holistic integration of qualitative and quantitative data sources is a significant challenge. Members of our team are currently involved in various developments in this area, including the OSMI working groups. It is expected that the expertise of these groups will make a substantial contribution to the development of an integrated data presentation strategy for the dashboard.

Once the data streams have been brought together, there are countless possibilities for visualization within the dashboard. Decisions about visualizations will be made in consultation with Open Science NL. The assignment also requires granularity at different levels of the organization. In each of the options, there is functionality for filtering at figure and data level. Furthermore, it is important to provide all elements in the dashboard with metadata, so that a user can find out where the data comes from (source), what the other properties of the underlying data are (definitions) and when the data was generated (timestamp). Depending on the type of user, the data is not only offered visually (dashboard), but we can also make the data available via an API. By offering this documented, the data becomes easily accessible to users who want to analyse the data themselves and/or want to link their reading applications to the monitor.

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